

D2.3 Methodology for jointly training FIR and response generator

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Abstract	<p>This report summarizes research within the ELOQUENCE project on factual information retrieval (FIR) with conversational/speech queries and the design of a modern, LLM-based dialogue manager. A key contribution is a speech-enabled methodology for the joint training of information retrieval and response generation components, which utilizes a connector-based architecture that was developed within the WP2 and presented in previous deliverables. The resulting system outperforms text-only baselines, although it introduces challenges in maintaining retrieval performance. To address data scarcity and mitigate system bias, the report introduces novel methods for creating controlled training data, including a framework for generating psychologically coherent user personas based on Italian demographic data and the SDialog Python library for creating reproducible, orchestrated synthetic dialogues. Finally, the report outlines the architecture for an LLM-based Dialogue Manager designed to orchestrate the conversational system and discusses its future integration into ELOQUENCE pilots.</p>		

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Table of Contents

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
2	INTRODUCTION.....	9
3	METHODOLOGY FOR JOINT TRAINING OF FIR AND RESPONSE GENERATOR	10
3.1	DATASET.....	10
3.2	METHODOLOGY FOR JOINT TRAINING	11
3.2.1	<i>Joint system architecture.....</i>	<i>11</i>
3.2.2	<i>Question-answering branch pretraining</i>	<i>12</i>
3.3	CASCADED TEXT-ONLY BASELINE	13
3.3.1	<i>Retriever.....</i>	<i>13</i>
3.3.2	<i>Reader.....</i>	<i>13</i>
3.4	EXPERIMENTAL SETUP	14
3.5	RESULTS AND ANALYSIS.....	15
3.6	SUMMARY AND FUTURE WORK.....	16
4	SYNTHETIC PERSONA GENERATION.....	17
4.1	MOTIVATION.....	17
4.2	METHODOLOGICAL BASIS.....	17
4.3	LLM GENERATION AND EXAMPLES.....	18
4.4	DATA ANALYSIS.....	20
4.5	SUMMARY	26
5	A PYTHON LIBRARY FOR SYNTHETIC DIALOG GENERATION.....	27
5.1	MOTIVATION.....	27
5.2	THE SDIALOG LIBRARY	27
5.2.1	<i>Dialogue Data Structures.....</i>	<i>27</i>
5.2.2	<i>Personas and Agents</i>	<i>28</i>
5.2.3	<i>Orchestration.....</i>	<i>29</i>
5.2.4	<i>Dialogue Generation.....</i>	<i>30</i>
5.2.5	<i>Datasets and Scenarios.....</i>	<i>31</i>
5.3	PRACTICAL EXAMPLES	32
5.3.1	<i>Example 1: Basic Persona-based Dialogue.....</i>	<i>32</i>
5.3.2	<i>Example 2: Multi-Agent Dialogue with Orchestration</i>	<i>33</i>
5.3.3	<i>Example 3: Scenario-Driven Dialogue Generation with STAR Dataset.....</i>	<i>34</i>
5.3.4	<i>Example 4: Exporting and Loading Dialogues</i>	<i>35</i>
5.3.5	<i>Example 5: Custom Orchestrators.....</i>	<i>35</i>
5.4	SUMMARY	36
6	DIALOG MANAGER ARCHITECTURE AND INTEGRATION	37
6.1	CURRENT STATE-OF-THE-ART FOR LLM-BASED DIALOG MANAGER ARCHITECTURE.....	37
6.1.1	<i>LLM-based Dialog Manager Systems</i>	<i>37</i>
6.1.2	<i>Multilingual Dialog Manager Systems</i>	<i>37</i>
6.1.3	<i>Dialog Summarization</i>	<i>38</i>
6.1.4	<i>Out-Of-Domain Detection.....</i>	<i>38</i>
6.1.5	<i>Requests For Missing or Ambiguous Information</i>	<i>39</i>
6.2	PROPOSED DIALOG MANAGER ARCHITECTURE	39
6.2.1	<i>Experiments on Dialog Summarization</i>	<i>41</i>
6.3	INTEGRATION INTO ELOQUENCE PILOTS	43
6.4	SUMMARY	44
7	CONCLUSIONS.....	45
8	REFERENCES.....	46

List of figures

Figure 3-1. Joint spoken retrieval/QA system architecture. The retrieval branch is trained with knowledge distillation against the outputs of the M3 encoder on text inputs, the QA branch is trained using cross-entropy. 11

Figure 3-2. Diagram of the two connector pretraining schemes: the CTC-based pretraining (A) and the standard LLM-based ASR objective (B). 12

Figure 3-3 Prompt for the Reader Language Model..... 14

Figure 3-4: Example of model input. 14

Figure 3-5 Exact-match (EM) and token-level F1 performance comparison among our text baseline and speech-based retrieval/QA systems on the SQA-5 dataset. 15

Figure 4-1 – Boxplot representing the differences to interpret and express personality traits among censored and uncensored LLMs. 21

Figure 4-2 – Pipeline of the experimental comparison between semi and full synthetic generated personas. 21

Figure 4-3 - Boxplots comparing the ability of LLMs (Mixtral and DarkLlama) to generate synthetic BFI response dataset (output of Step 1) with respect to Real BFI response dataset..... 23

Figure 4-4 - Distribution of similarity and BLEU scores across all pairs of generated biographies..... 24

Figure 4-5 - Relationship between semantic similarity (cosine similarity) and lexical similarity (BLEU score). 25

Figure 6-1: The IP architecture is designed in a modular way. Our implementations are wrapped in virtual containers running on the same machine to ensure fast communication. To achieve modularity, the expected means of communication is via API. 43

List of tables

Table 1: Dialog Summarization Evaluation Results 42

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ASR	Automatic Speech Recognition
BFI	Big Five Inventory
CTC	Connectionist Temporal Classification
DM	Dialog Manager
DST	Dialog State Tracking
FIR	Factual Information Retrieval
LLM	Large Language Model
MSE	Mean Square Error
NLM	Neural Language Model
NLP	Natural Language Processing
ODM	Open-Domain Dialog
OOD	Out-of-domain
QA	Question Answering
TOD	Task-Oriented Dialog

1 Executive Summary

This report summarizes research and experimental efforts related to WP2, Tasks 2 and 3 that are focused on Factual information retrieval (FIR) with conversational queries and designing a modern LLM-based dialog manager, respectively. We are also exploring novel methods for creating synthetic persona models and present a toolkit able to leverage such models to create artificial dialogs. This is in line with our continued efforts to address the bias of the developed systems by creating data in a controlled way and, at the same time, overcoming the ever-lasting problem of the lack of real and annotated training data.

In Chapter 3, we focus on the central topic of this deliverable, which is the methodology for jointly training information retrieval and response generator components. We base our model design on previously developed codebase reported in D2.1 and D2.2 where we interconnected standard text-based LLMs with a speech modality. More specifically, we extend the methodology and architecture for speech-enabled FIR from D2.2 with the capability to generate a response to the query. The resulting architecture can, therefore, again accept speech or text queries, but this time, it also contains a branch to generate a response to that query. This connector-based system outperforms text-only baselines, though the joint training process can slightly degrade the performance of the retrieval component, which we see as a challenge for further research. Note that similarly to D 2.2, we keep the foundational models frozen (original FIR system and LLM) frozen which enables its use with text as it was originally developed, as well as with speech input which promotes multi-modality and is in line with **KR2** (Multimodality) in **Objective1** (*Advanced SLU technologies for safety-critical applications*).

In Chapter 4, we present a methodology for creating realistic user persona models that leverage Italian demographic data to generate psychologically coherent biographies and simulate diverse users. A motivation for this research is to evaluate social biases in AI systems and later apply this methodology in an Eloquence Pilot 2: *Social context-aware language model detecting biases*. This line of research is aligned with **KR8** (Reliability/trust of generic LLMs) in **Objective 3** (*Enhanced conversational agents toward un-biased and trustworthy dialogues with end-users*) and will contribute to efforts of achieving **KR10** (Mitigate by 50% the bias in deployed models).

In Chapter 5, we introduce *SDialog*, a Python library for creating reproducible synthetic dialogues which has the capacity to leverage persona models discussed above. This toolkit allows for controlled, persona-driven conversations and includes an "orchestrator" to manage conversation flow and simulate specific user behaviors. Generating such synthetic dialog data will contribute to adapting existing foundational models to the dialog tasks and is therefore aligned with **KR3** (Adaptation of LLMs) in **Objective1** (*Advanced SLU technologies for safety-critical applications*).

Finally, in Chapter 6, we describe the proposed LLM-based architecture of the central component of the dialogue system – the Dialogue Manager, which orchestrates the entire conversational flow. Apart from the modular architecture, we also discuss the problem of efficiency and LLM context limits and propose a solution based on pruning long conversation histories via summarization. In the end, we also outline an integration of the DM into Eloquence pilots and demonstrate how the system's advanced capabilities will be deployed and evaluated in real-world multilingual and multi-domain scenarios.

2 Introduction

In this deliverable, we provide a comprehensive overview of several methodologies and components that we develop to advance conversational dialogue systems within the ELOQUENCE project. We start by presenting our continued efforts in advancing the state of research in spoken Factual Information Retrieval (FIR). In chapter 3, we enter the central topic of this deliverable, which is the joint training of an FIR and a Response Generator components. This section explores novel system architecture and methodology for pretraining strategies aimed at improving the synergy between retrieving relevant information and formulating an accurate answer in open-domain spoken question-answering tasks.

Later in this document, we are again detailing newly developed methodologies for generating high-quality synthetic data that are crucial for fast development by creating realistic training and evaluation materials that are required to build a robust system capable of handling complex, spoken interactions. In chapter 4, we describe a methodology for creating realistic user profiles grounded in the Big Five psychological model (Goldberg, The development of markers for the Big-Five factor structure., 1992). This approach generates psychologically coherent personas and detailed biographical narratives, providing a rich basis for creating dialogue scenarios designed to test for social biases in AI systems. In chapter 5, we bring the data generation models into practice and introduce an SDialog toolkit designed to standardize and streamline the creation of synthetic dialogues. This chapter also explains how the library uses the personas, providing abstractions for agents and orchestration controls to manage conversation flow while ensuring that dialogue generation is reproducible and controllable, facilitating rigorous experimentation.

Finally, in chapter 6, the report describes the central component, the Dialog Manager (DM), that brings all the pieces together and acts as the orchestrator for the entire conversational flow. This chapter details the DM's responsibilities, including managing the dialogue state, handling out-of-domain requests, requesting clarification for ambiguous queries, and pruning conversation history through summarization. It explains how the DM integrates the retriever and response generator, coordinating their functions through the ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground interface for final deployment in the project's pilots

3 Methodology for joint training of FIR and Response Generator

In this chapter, we demonstrate the joint factual information retrieval (FIR) and response generation methodology on simple open-domain question-answering (QA) systems, which implement a simple retrieval-augmented generation-based RAG paradigm: the retriever selects K candidate documents based on the given spoken user query, the retrieved documents are added to the query and the constructed prompt is given to a downstream LLM, which is tasked with extracting the correct answer to the user query based on the retrieved documents.

This joint approach has a small caveat – for joint training of both systems, the most natural approach is to share some parts of the model between both the retrieval and QA branches, as there is no supervision/conditioning signal going from the QA branch to the retriever branch. In contrast, for example when applied to a spoken dialogue tracking/response system, there, in fact, is such a signal, as given the user query, the dialogue system first predicts the dialogue state, which can then be used along with the user query as input to the retrieval system. This way, the retriever performance is dependent on the dialogue state tracking performance of the LLM. The retriever can then select documents that are more appropriate to the actual situation in the dialogue. When the retrieved material is passed back to the LLM, it can, in turn, facilitate a higher quality response to the original query. Therefore, both branches of the system are co-dependent in terms of performance in this scenario.

However, there is currently no suitable dataset for running such experiments, as most dialogue state tracking datasets either do not have the speech component at all (and the only way to address this would be to resort to TTS, which carries some domain generalization risks), or do not contain a knowledge base suitable for retrieval, as typically, external information available to the agent takes the form of a simple database (e.g. lists of named entities, location addresses).

In the presented simpler open-domain QA scenario, joint training will simply encompass the joint adaptation of the speech encoder for producing suitable speech representations for both the retrieval and the QA branches of the system, ensuring better target domain adaptation, while allowing us to use only a single speech encoder model and therefore reuse the same embedding sequence extracted from the speech for both system branches.

Once again, we rely on the concept of connectors – small networks that project the output embeddings from one foundation model (speech encoder) to the input embedding space of another foundation model (LLM). Typically, the foundation models are kept (mostly) frozen during training and only the parameters of the connectors are tuned for the target task. For more information about the connectors and their applications to different tasks (such as ASR, dialogue state tracking, retrieval), please refer to deliverables D2.1 and D2.2, where they are discussed at length.

Similar joint retrieval and response generation training paradigms have already been demonstrated in prior work (Zhang, et al., 2022), (Siriwardhana, et al., 2023), (Shi T., et al., 2023), typically with elaborate objectives and conditioning of the response generator on the retriever output as its being trained. However, jointly trained systems can, in general, be more difficult to implement efficiently from the engineering standpoint and more difficult to optimize and keep from degrading during training. It is not uncommon for separately trained systems to ultimately provide comparable performance for an ultimately lower training cost, and whether to use similar joint training methodologies is probably best to decide on an individual case-by-case basis.

3.1 Dataset

The open-domain QA experiments are conducted on the SLUE-SQA-5 dataset (Shon, et al., 2023). SLUE-SQA-5 is a spoken question answering (QA) dataset from SLUE Phase2. It comprises approximately 50,000 QA pairs derived from five well-known text QA datasets—SQuAD, Natural Questions, TriviaQA, WebQuestions, and CuratedTREC. Spoken questions were collected via crowdsourcing from human speakers using Amazon Mechanical Turk, ensuring natural speech input. Spoken documents paired with these questions were sourced from the Spoken Wikipedia corpus. The dataset includes fine-tuning, development, and test splits, with a verified test subset manually annotated to confirm the presence of answer evidence. We used this same dataset already in deliverable 2.2 for our base spoken retrieval experiments and now extend that work to the full open-domain QA task.

For pretraining the connectors, we once again use the Mozilla Common Voice 15 (Ardila, et al., 2020) speech recognition dataset, specifically its English subset.

3.2 Methodology for joint training

3.2.1 Joint system architecture

Our joint retrieval-QA system has two branches, as depicted in Figure 3-1:

- The **retrieval** branch
- The **question-answering** (QA) branch

The first branch (A) encompasses the input speech encoder (Whisper-large-v3), a text embedding model (BGE-M3) and the corresponding connector network mapping the speech representations from the speech encoder output space to the input representation space of the text embedding model. Same as in deliverable 2.2, the retrieval branch of the system is trained using the same knowledge distillation objective (MSE, contrastive cosine loss) between the output speech-based query representations and the embedding representations of the corresponding ground truth text. Upon inference, the output embeddings of the M3 encoder (denoted in blue in the figure) are used to retrieve the text documents that are used as input to the QA LLM. We build upon the connector-based spoken retrieval system that was presented in deliverable 2.2 and use it as the starting checkpoint for the retrieval branch of the system.

The QA branch (B) utilizes the same speech encoder but uses a separate connector network to transform the speech representations to the input embedding space of a downstream LLM. This LLM (Llama-3.1-8B-instruct) additionally takes the retrieved documents as input and is tasked with extracting the answer to the given user query from these supplied documents. For our baseline system described in Section 3.3, we only use zero-shot (or few-shot) prompting, no fine-tuning is performed. In the joint/aligned setting, the connector provides some fine-tuning capacity for the model, while not really disrupting its original capabilities.

Figure 3-1. Joint spoken retrieval/QA system architecture. The retrieval branch is trained with knowledge distillation against the outputs of the M3 encoder on text inputs, the QA branch is trained using cross-entropy.

Keeping the LLM frozen ensures that its capabilities remain unchanged, making it possible that the same LLM instance is used for several downstream tasks. Additionally, it ensures much lower computational resource requirements as the number of parameters that are being tuned for the whole joint retrieval/QA system is approximately 100 million compared to the 9 billion parameters that constitute the whole model.

3.2.2 Question-answering branch pretraining

As for all connector-based aligned systems, the QA branch connector must be pretrained using some general data to properly initialize the connector, as the amount of downstream task fine-tuning data is usually limited compared to the available amount of, for example, speech recognition data. As the final prompting scheme of the QA branch is the same as for the text-only baseline from Section 3.3 and it is at the same time desirable for the LLM to actually benefit from the supplied prompt so that it adheres to the given task constraints, we pretrain the QA connector in a way that minimizes the risk of the connector task-overfitting phenomenon and sets it up for further fine-tuning on the open-domain QA task.

In previous deliverables, the connector-LLM aligned system was typically pretrained using the ASR objective – the connector is tasked with soft-prompting the frozen LLM so that it generates the transcription of the given speech input. Here, we experiment with an alternative: a CTC-based approach, which enforces a much more explicit alignment between the output connector representations and the corresponding text-embedding representations of the ground truth text, defined by the downstream LLM. The whole LLM is discarded apart from its embedding layer, which is frozen and used as the CTC head for the training. The ground truth text is converted to tokens using the original LLM vocabulary and is used as the target for the CTC loss objective. The blank token embedding is trained separately, initialized as the mean of the embedding matrix. This way, it is effectively possible to still pretrain the connector for a task like ASR, and the output representations remain agnostic to the downstream LLM task, while still carrying the semantic content of the input speech utterance.

Figure 3-2. Diagram of the two connector pretraining schemes: the CTC-based pretraining (A) and the standard LLM-based ASR objective (B).

The downside of this approach is that the CTC-based pretraining seems to be a very difficult task to optimize for, compared to the standard LLM-based ASR approach. The embedding matrices of LLMs like Llama-3.1-8B have much larger vocabulary sizes (128k tokens) compared to standard CTC modelling heads (often character-level vocabularies). Additionally, the connector has to approximate a space of much higher dimensionality, as the hidden size of the connector is typically 1024 and the hidden size of the Llama-3.1-8B model is 4096. It is also standard to tune the parameters of the CTC head during training, which is not possible to do here, as the goal of the pretraining is to match the speech representations to their textual counterparts as they enter the downstream LLM, not just optimize for ASR performance in general.

In general, though the LLM is not present, and it is therefore not necessary to propagate through it during training, the training takes a long time to converge due to the issues mentioned above. Additionally, we encounter some challenges with the AdamW optimizer getting stuck in local optima due to slow convergence in general and the

“sluggishness” of momentum and the fact that the gradients tend to get very small due to the generally small lengths of the target embedding vectors. We found that simply resetting the optimizer state once this state of plateau is reached immediately helps the model to exit the local optimum and reach much better validation loss performance.

In our experiments, the CTC ASR performance is not enough to simply use the connector as a transcription head. We run standard CTC greedy decoding, which has the following steps:

1. Connector output projection to the most likely LLM tokens using argmax
2. Repeated symbol removal
3. Blank symbol removal

This way, our models achieve on average 30% WER, which is not a level of performance usable for ASR purposes only, however, the point of the CTC-based pretraining is to obtain a rough, but concrete alignment between the connector output representations and the LLM input embeddings, which is achieved. It is possible that this explicit alignment will be lost during subsequent fine-tuning for QA, as the connector will also learn to soft-prompt the LLM for the target task.

3.3 Cascaded text-only baseline

To establish an upper bound with the available transcriptions of the SQA-5 (Shon, et al., 2023) dataset, we establish a zero-shot LLM baseline. The open-domain QA system is composed of (a) a retrieval system that provides search in the document storage, and (b) a reader LLM that is prompted to answer the question using the sequence of top-k documents retrieved from system (a).

3.3.1 Retriever

We use the single-vector models ranked highly in the Massive Text Embedding Benchmark (Muennighoff, Tazi, Magne, & Reimers, 2023). Firstly, we use the BGE-m3 system (Chen, et al., 2024), with the training data publicly released¹. The model is based on a multilingual BERT-like model, XLM-Roberta (279M parameters). Secondly, we choose an LLM retrieval-based system NV-Embed-V2 (Lee, et al., 2025), which fine-tunes Mistral-7B-0.1 (7.24B parameters).

In both cases, all documents are encoded with a document encoder. Maximum inner-product search is performed to find the ranked list of top-K. We reported on the difference between these two retrievers and compared them with spoken retrieval systems already in deliverable D2.2. For our final spoken QA systems, we conduct experiments with both the text-based M3 (as well as NV-Embed-v2) retriever, and its speech-adapted counterpart that was trained for D2.2.

3.3.2 Reader

The top-K results from the retriever are then fed to the “reader” system. In this work, the reader system is instruction-tuned LLM Llama3.1-Instruct 8B (Grattafiori, et al., 2024). We prompt the language model in zero-shot setting with the following instruction format shown in Figure 3-3.

¹ <https://huggingface.co/datasets/Shitao/bge-m3-data>

```
"From the following documents, extract the exact phrase that answers the question. "  
"Do not paraphrase or add information. Finish your answer with \n\n. Provide a short snippet. \n\n"  
"{docs}\n"  
"Question: {question}\n"  
"Answer:"
```

Figure 3-3 Prompt for the Reader Language Model

The model is prompted in a chat template setting. A **chat template** is a structured way to convert a conversation into a format that the model understands at inference time. Each model family (like LLaMA, ChatGPT, Claude, etc.) uses slightly different prompt formats. Figure 3-4 illustrates the input to the language model before tokenization.

```
<|begin_of_text|><|start_header_id|>system<|end_header_id|> You are a helpful assistant. <|eot_id|>  
<|start_header_id|>user<|end_header_id|> From the following documents, extract the exact phrase that answers  
the question. Do not paraphrase or add information. Finish your answer with \n\n. Provide a short snippet. [Rank  
#1-Document "France"]: The capital of France is Paris, which is known for its art, fashion, and the Eiffel Tower. [Rank  
#2-Document "Germany"]: Berlin is the capital of Germany. [Rank #3-Document "Spain"]: Madrid is the political and  
cultural center of Spain. Question: What is the capital of France? Answer: <|eot_id|>  
<|start_header_id|>assistant<|end_header_id|>
```

Figure 3-4: Example of model input.

3.4 Experimental setup

We base our fine-tuned models on the text-only baseline system, utilizing the M3 encoder as the retriever foundation model and Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct as the QA foundational model. As shown in Figure 3-1, we construct the joint retrieval/QA pipeline with these foundation models, where both branches of the system share the same speech encoder (Whisper-large-v3), and each branch of the system uses its own dedicated connector. Both connectors have the same architecture: 6x downsampling factor, 2 layers, hidden size of 1024, 16 attention heads, intermediate linear layer dimension 4096. The prompting scheme is the same as for the text-only baselines, with small changes in the agent response section of the prompt, over which the loss is computed, as we found it extremely beneficial to train the model for also explicitly producing the transcription of the speech contained in the supplied speech embeddings.

We experiment with three different retriever setups. First, our fine-tuned systems are evaluated using the base text-only M3 retriever to obtain topline performance for the given system, as the work presented in D2.2 showed that the speech-based retrieval setup lacks some performance compared to the base text-only scenario. Then we use the best speech-based M3 retrieval system from D2.2, which was fine-tuned on the SQA-5 dataset to measure performance in the non-joint retrieval/QA training scenario, and finally, we evaluate with the same retrieval system, which was further fine-tuned in the joint scenario. The training objective for the retrieval system remains the same as in D2.2, leveraging MSE and contrastive cosine distance loss designed to match the speech-based and text-based dense embedding representations at the output of the M3 encoder.

When training the QA branch of the systems, we run two separate sets of experiments. First, we only train the connector, without training the retriever. This is to identify the best strategy for training the QA branch as initially there were issues with the CTC pretraining strategy that we took. Originally, we attempted to only train the model to produce the extracted response from the documents, however, this turned out to not be a strong enough supervision signal for the connector/speech encoder, as the response typically only contains 5 to 10 tokens at max. Though our hope was that the CTC-based connector pretraining would more explicitly represent the actual textual information in the embeddings so that some inference time can be saved by not producing the transcription, the models would simply not converge to anything meaningful in this scenario. On the other hand, training the model to also produce the transcript for the given user query solves this issue and the model converges in a few thousand steps.

The second set of experiments trains the QA branch already in the joint QA/retriever scenario, where we additionally unfreeze the last layer of the whisper speech encoder, to fine-tune it to produce better speech representations for both branches jointly.

The QA connector is always first pretrained for ASR on Common Voice 15 using CTC (the CTC head consisting of the frozen Llama input embedding matrix). The checkpoint used to initialize the retriever branch of the system was originally pretrained on Common Voice and subsequently fine-tuned on the SQA-5 dataset.

All training runs for the QA system (both in joint and non-joint settings) use batch size of 24 – each experiment is run on two Nvidia RTX 6000 Ada 48GB GPUs with batch size of 3 and 4 gradient accumulation steps. We train with a learning rate of 1e-4 and 1000 warmup steps and utilize early stopping to avoid overfitting. For training, we set the number of retrieved documents to 5 (sorted by rank as assigned by the retriever) and make sure that the ground truth document is always present in this set. If not, we use it to replace one of the five retrieved documents at random.

3.5 Results and analysis

A comparison between the baselines described in Section 3.3 and our trained systems is shown in Figure 3-5. We evaluate all models using exact-match (EM, hit if the prediction and ground truth match exactly, otherwise miss) and token level F1 score.

The M3 and NV-Embed text-based zero-shot baselines are depicted in blue and orange colors, respectively. Increasing the number of retrieved documents in the context of the LLM improves the performance steadily, but the performance plateaus for K larger than 30. We hypothesize that the reason for this is that at that point, the task shifts more towards a needle in a haystack type of problem, rather than factual QA. Additionally, the retrievers also typically plateau for K larger than e.g. 40, so the benefit of adding more documents to the context is minimal.

The overall performance of the zero-shot baselines does not really come close to any of the fine-tuned models. However, as the observed fine-tuning performance gain is ultimately a question of better aligning the QA model to the QA task, the only other way to improve it for the baselines without training would be to employ a few-shot prompting strategy. Compared to training the connector, however, such an approach is not ideal as it dramatically increases the inference cost and vastly overshadows the cost increase caused by processing the speech embedding sequence in the aligned connector scenario, compared to the shorter string of text tokens representing the query in the zero-shot setting.

Figure 3-5 Exact-match (EM) and token-level F1 performance comparison among our text baseline and speech-based retrieval/QA systems on the SQA-5 dataset.

We train one system only using the QA objective and use the baseline text-only M3 retriever to supply the retrieved document upon evaluation to better understand the topline performance for this experimental setup. This system significantly outperforms the text-based baselines, as shown in Figure 3-5, but appears to plateau much quicker, already at 10 retrieved documents. One possible explanation for this would be that the models do not generalize to different numbers of retrieved documents in their input context well, as during training, we set $k=5$. This should, however, be easy to address by simply varying this number already during training.

Then, we train a retriever/QA already in the joint scenario, optimizing for both the knowledge-distillation and the QA cross-entropy objectives at the same time with equal weights. We find that optimizing such a system poses several challenges, as it becomes relatively easy for the retriever to start overfitting or showing signs of degradation upon fine-tuning. This is mostly due to the two objectives being too dissimilar in terms of values and therefore also gradients and further experiments need to be performed to fully address the issue. Nevertheless, when evaluating this jointly trained QA system using the base text-only M3 retriever, we observe some marginal performance gains over the individually trained system, specifically for $k=5$. Other than that, the performance is comparable.

Evaluating this jointly trained QA system with the base speech retriever checkpoint from D2.2, we observe some EM and F1 performance degradation, which is to be expected as this speech-adapted retriever performs worse compared to the standard text-only model. Finally, employing the jointly trained retriever in the evaluation, there is some further performance degradation for lower k values, which indicates that more work needs to be done to ensure that the performance of the retriever does not degrade during training. There are several possible explanations for this degradation, one being that the learning rates/gradients should be scaled in a manner that ensures balanced training between the two system branches. Additionally, a better negative mining strategy for the contrastive cosine loss of the retriever should be explored as it seems that due to the nature and size of the joint system, the individual batches are too small to provide enough in-batch negatives for this objective.

When no relevant documents are supplied, we still observe performance increases over the zero-shot baselines, which again demonstrates the task adaptation capabilities of the connectors.

3.6 Summary and future work

We demonstrate a joint retrieval/QA training pipeline, which relies on a single speech encoder, that takes the given user query as input and extracts a sequence of hidden representations to be further processed by two jointly trained branches: a retrieval branch and a QA branch. The retrieval branch consists of a small connector network used to project the speech embedding sequence into the word embedding space of a standard text retriever, producing a dense embedding representation of the user query, which is used to retrieve the top K relevant documents. These documents are then passed to the LLM in the QA branch of the system along with the original speech embeddings that are projected to the LLM representation space using a second, independent connector.

We find that our connector-based spoken QA system significantly outperforms the zero-shot text-only baseline, providing much better performance even for lower values of K . At the same time, we find it challenging to correctly control the joint training phase, observing some minor performance degradations in the speech retrieval branch compared to the isolated training case, possibly due to imperfect gradient/learning rate scaling for the retrieval branch. At the same time, given that the retrieval branch was previously fine-tuned to saturation with the KD objective on the SQA-5 dataset, such minor performance degradations are perhaps not too surprising. We continue working on addressing these issues, and plan on developing more thorough guidelines for mitigating the retriever performance degradation using better defined and stronger objectives.

4 Synthetic persona generation

4.1 Motivation

The development of synthetic dialogue systems for social bias detection presents the challenge of generating diverse, representative user interactions that reflect the complexity of real human behavior.

Traditional approaches to bias detection often rely on limited datasets that may not capture the full spectrum of social dynamics, personality variations, and interaction patterns present in real-world scenarios. For this reason, within the context of Pilot 2, we exploit synthetic persona generation as a basis for creating realistic dialogue scenarios that can reveal latent social biases in conversational AI systems.

The strategy focuses on creating personas with defined psychological profiles to explore how different personality types interact with dialogue systems. This helps identify potential biases in specific social contexts or user characteristics. Persona-driven dialogue generation allows us to control variables like personality traits and demographics while ensuring natural interactions. This approach is crucial for thorough bias testing, enabling the exploration of edge cases and minority perspectives often overlooked in real user data. Additionally, synthetic personas facilitate scalable generation of diverse interactions for effective bias detection, ensuring consistent analysis across various scenarios and experimental conditions.

4.2 Methodological Basis

Our approach to synthetic persona generation takes inspiration from established literature on human-computer interaction. Specifically, the Personas methodology has been developed within the HCI research community to provide a framework for modelling fictional user archetypes that represent distinct user groups with specific characteristics, behaviors, and needs (Salminen, Guan, Jung, & Jansen, 2021; Cooper & Reimann, 2023; Jansen, Salminen, Jung, & Guan, 2022). Traditionally, the Personas methodology addresses user representation by transforming demographic and psychographic data, collected on the field, into concrete, actionable character profiles. This methodology integrates behavioral patterns, motivational factors, and contextual preferences into coherent user archetypes.

In the context of Pilot 2, we explored a methodology for instructing LLMs to generate synthetic data that offers several key advantages. First, the Personas framework provides a structured approach to ensure that generated personas are internally consistent while also representing a diverse range of user characteristics. By employing simple prompt engineering techniques, we can introduce necessary variations in parameters to produce distinct user attributes. This approach helps avoid the creation of unrealistic or contradictory character combinations.

By clearly identifying the attributes of personas and how they relate to one another, researchers can create targeted variations that explore specific aspects of user behavior, while keeping the overall persona coherent. Additionally, combining large language models (LLMs) with the personas methodology allows the integration of psychological models into the generation process.

Psychological personality models provide the essential framework for creating psychologically grounded synthetic personas. Among the available personality frameworks, the Big Five model (Goldberg, The development of markers for the Big-Five factor structure., 1992) offers a particularly robust foundation due to its empirical validation, cross-cultural applicability, and comprehensive coverage of personality dimensions.

The Big Five model describes personality using five main traits: Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Emotional Stability. Each trait reflects different parts of how people behave and think, allowing us to understand personalities better.

- Openness to Experience shows how curious someone is, their appreciation for beauty, aesthetics, and cultural experiences, and their willingness to try new things. This trait affects how people handle new information, creative tasks, and unusual situations in conversations.
- Conscientiousness relates to being disciplined, focused on goals, and organized. People with different levels of conscientiousness will engage with tasks, pay attention to detail, and show persistence differently in conversations.

- Extraversion measures how social, assertive, and energetic someone is. This trait greatly impacts how people communicate, take social initiatives, and respond in conversations.
- Agreeableness reflects how cooperative, empathetic, and trusting someone is with others. This trait influences how people deal with conflict, work with others, and understand social cues in dialogues.
- Emotional Stability (often measured as its inverse, Neuroticism) indicates resilience to stress, emotional volatility, and anxiety levels. This dimension influences how personas handle challenging situations, uncertainty, and potential system failures.

4.3 LLM Generation and Examples

The synthetic persona generation pipeline employs a two-stage process designed to create psychologically coherent character profiles. The initial stage involves personality trait elicitation, where large language models are instructed to respond to standardized personality assessments from specific psychological perspectives. The second stage transforms these personality profiles into detailed biographical narratives that implicitly express the measured traits.

Step 1. During the personality trait elicitation phase, large language model is asked to assume the role of a person with predefined personality characteristics and receive the task to complete a personality questionnaire. The Big Five Inventory (BFI) provides a standardized measurement instrument for quantifying these personality dimensions. In our approach, we exploited the 50-item version. It ensures comprehensive trait assessment while maintaining practical feasibility for computational implementation. Each personality dimension is scored through validated psychometric procedures, enabling consistent persona characterization across different generation scenarios.

The models receive explicit instructions to adopt specific personality characteristics (called PERSONALITY_SEED) and respond to questionnaire items using a standardized Likert scale format. For generating the PERSONALITY_SEED, we adopted the approach proposed in Jiang et al. (Jiang, et al., 2023). It defines personality descriptions involving all BFI traits and each dimension is categorized into binary pairs: I) Extroverted / Introverted; II) Agreeable / Disagreeable; III) Conscientious / Unconscientious; IV) Neurotic / Emotionally Stable; and V) Open / Closed to Experience. All 32 possible combinations form distinct personality archetypes used as PERSONALITY_SEED parameters. For example, one seed specifies [introverted, agreeable, unconscientious, neurotic, open to experience], whilst another defines [extroverted, disagreeable, conscientious, emotionally stable, closed to experience]. Each personality seed is instantiated multiple times during questionnaire completion, enabling controlled trait generation and preserving natural variability within personality archetypes for robust synthetic personality dataset creation.

This structured approach ensures consistent response formatting and enables reliable score computation across different model implementations.

```
You are a character who is %PERSONALITY_SEED%.

Here are a number of characteristics that may or may not apply to you. For example, do you agree that you are someone who likes to spend time with others? Please respond with the exact same format below. Each characteristic should have a response in the form "(a) X\n(b) X\n(c) X\n...", where "X" is a number from 1 to 5 indicating how much you agree or disagree. Do not provide explanations or additional text "just the numbers in this exact format.

1 for Disagree, 2 for Slightly Disagree, 3 for Neutral, 4 for Slightly Agree, 5 for Agree.

(a) I am the life of the party
(b) I feel little concern for others
(c) I am always prepared
(d) I get stressed out easily
(e) I have a rich vocabulary
(f) I don't talk a lot
...
```

The personality questionnaire responses are then processed according to established psychometric procedures to generate quantitative trait scores.

Step 2. The biography generation phase transforms numerical personality scores into narrative descriptions that embody the specified traits without explicit mention of psychological constructs. The prompt also includes personality scores as input parameters and generates approximately 800-word biographical texts that naturally express the underlying personality characteristics through behavioral descriptions, life choices, and personal experiences.

```
You are a %GENDER% %AGE% year old student living in %REGION%. From the personality questionnaire, you obtained the following BFI scores: [Agreeableness= %AGRE%, Conscientiousness= %CONS%, Emotionally Stable= %EMO%, Extraversion= %EXTR%, Openness= %OPEN%]
```

```
Your responses to the personality questionnaire are the following:
```

- ```
(a) I am the life of the party: Disagree
(b) I feel little concern for others: Agree
(c) I am always prepared: Slightly Agree
(d) I get stressed out easily: Slightly Agree
(e) I have a rich vocabulary: Slightly Agree
(f) I don't talk a lot: Agree
...
```

```
Please share a personal biography in 800 words. Do not explicitly mention your personality traits in the biography.
```

To enhance the realism and demographic authenticity of synthetic personas, we systematically integrated empirically derived demographic distributions into the biography generation process. The values for %GENDER%, %AGE%, and %REGION% parameters were determined through comprehensive analysis of official Italian university enrollment data obtained from the Ministry of Education's ISTAT database, covering the 2023/2024 academic year<sup>2</sup>.

**Age distribution** was stratified across five categories based on actual enrollment patterns: 19-21 years (39%), 22-24 years (29%), 25-27 years (12%), 28-30 years (6%), and over 30 years (14%). This distribution reflects the natural demographic composition of Italian higher education, ensuring that generated personas represent realistic age profiles rather than arbitrary age assignments.

**Gender distribution** follows the documented patterns in Italian universities, with 56.7% female and 43.3% male representation, accurately reflecting the contemporary gender composition in higher education contexts.

**Regional distribution.** It simplifies the current geographical spread of Italian university students, ensuring that personas originate with similar weights from four representative Italian areas (north, center, south and islands).

Here we report a couple of examples of biography coming out from the synthetic process.

Profile 1:

- Age: 18, Woman, from North of Italy
- Agreeableness= 4.9, Conscientiousness= 4.1, Emotionally\_Stable= 1.9, Extraversion= 2.4, Openness= 5.0.

```
I was born and raised in the beautiful region of Lombardia, Italy. My parents, both teachers, instilled in me a love for learning and exploration from a young age. I grew up surrounded by books, art supplies, and fascinating conversation, all of which contributed to my insatiable curiosity and open-mindedness.
...
```

```
In high school, I became involved in various extracurricular activities,
```

---

<sup>2</sup> <https://ustat.mur.gov.it/opendata/>

including debate club, drama club, and volunteer organizations, further nurturing my social skills and empathetic nature.

...

I have an older brother who is currently studying engineering, and our lively debates and discussions have helped shape my critical thinking abilities and strong convictions. I participated in several study abroad programs, including exchanges in France and Spain, which allowed me to become fluent in both languages and develop a deep appreciation for cultural diversity.

...

Ultimately, I believe that my unique blend of intellectual curiosity, emotional intelligence, and interpersonal skills will enable me to thrive in both personal and professional settings. I look forward to the challenges and rewards that lie ahead, knowing that my innate qualities and learned experiences will guide me towards a fulfilling and purpose-driven life.

#### Profile 2:

- Age: 19, Man, from Center of Italy
- Agreeableness= 1.5, Conscientiousness= 3.2, Emotionally\_Stable= 2.3, Extraversion= 3.6, Openness= 3.1

I was born and raised in the beautiful region of Campania, Italy, surrounded by the vibrant culture, delicious food, and breathtaking landscapes that the area is known for.

...

Growing up, I was an average student who didn't particularly excel in any specific subject but had a genuine curiosity and passion for learning new things. As I navigated my teenage years, I found myself drawn to the arts, literature, and music, often spending hours engrossed in books, painting, or playing the guitar.

...

Despite my love for the arts, I understood the importance of a well-rounded education and worked diligently to maintain decent grades. My parents encouraged me to explore various extracurricular activities, allowing me to discover my leadership skills and ability to connect with people from diverse backgrounds. Through these experiences, I gained confidence and developed a strong sense of self, realizing that I could positively impact those around me.

...

Eventually, I decided to pursue higher education to further expand my knowledge and skills.

...

## 4.4 Data Analysis

We defined an evaluation framework incorporating various experiments to evaluate different perspectives of persona generation.

**Ability to express Personality.** A first analysis of the generated personas has revealed distinct patterns in how different language models interpret and express personality traits. The comparative evaluation demonstrates that models exhibit varying capabilities in trait expression, with some dimensions proving more challenging to convey than others (see Figure 4-1). Extraversion and Emotional Stability show broader score distributions, indicating that models can effectively differentiate between high and low levels of these traits.



Figure 4-1 – Boxplot representing the differences to interpret and express personality traits among censored and uncensored LLMs.

For instance, the trait of conscientiousness presents challenges with models showing tendency toward positive trait expression regardless of input scores. This pattern suggests inherent biases in language model training that favor socially desirable characteristics. Similarly, Agreeableness demonstrates consistent positive skewing, reflecting potential limitations in generating personalities with challenging interpersonal characteristics.

The analysis reveals important differences between censored and uncensored model variants. Models with reduced content restrictions demonstrate greater variability in trait expression, particularly for characteristics traditionally considered negative or socially undesirable. This finding has significant implications for bias detection applications, where authentic representation of diverse personality types is essential for comprehensive system evaluation.



Figure 4-2 – Pipeline of the experimental comparison between semi and full synthetic generated personas.

**Full-Synthetic versus Semi-Synthetic.** A second comparison has been tried by confronting the generated biographies (hereafter called full synthetic) with a semi-synthetic version. For the semi-synthetic generation, we

adopted a freely available dataset of real user BFI responses<sup>3</sup>. This dataset contains users' real data, meaning that the BFI scores are computed by considering real responses collected from 2016 to 2018 through an interactive online personality test constructed by the International Personality Item Pool (IPIP) (Goldberg, et al., 2006). For our comparative analysis, we implemented a systematic sampling strategy to ensure representativeness whilst maintaining methodological rigor. The dataset was first filtered by nationality criteria, focusing on Italian respondents to create cultural consistency within our target demographic. This initial filtering yielded approximately 5,300 valid questionnaires. Subsequently, data cleaning procedures removed incomplete or inconsistent responses, resulting in a refined dataset of 4,571 complete personality profiles. Finally, to select approximately 320 representative questionnaires that would mirror the synthetic generation sample size, we employed a two-stage clustering approach. K-means analysis partitioned the cleaned dataset into distinct personality groupings, followed by quartile-based stratification within each cluster.

Finally, we have established two parallel pipelines (see Figure 4-2) for full and semi synthetic generation. The semi-synthetic generation skips step 1 and uses only the process described in step 2. Both pipelines converge to the biography creation, with identical prompting strategies and computational parameters. The BFI scores—whether derived from authentic human responses or synthetic generation—serve as standardised inputs for biographical narrative production. This methodological design isolates the impact of personality score origin whilst controlling for generation model variability.

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<sup>3</sup> The Dataset is available at: <http://ipip.ori.org/>



Figure 4-3 - Boxplots comparing the ability of LLMs (Mixtral and DarkLlama) to generate synthetic BFI response dataset (output of Step 1) with respect to Real BFI response dataset.

**Personality Score Alignment.** A first analysis that we conducted, concerns comparing the responses of Step 1 (i.e. the synthetic BFI response dataset) with real data coming from the IPIP's dataset (i.e. the Real BFI response dataset) with the intent of evaluating whether synthetic personality score distributions align with authentic human psychological patterns, providing validation for the underlying generation methodology. The experimental design involved generating 320 BFI scores for each model configuration (Mixtral and DarkLlama) through the personality questionnaire completion process described in Step 1. These synthetic datasets were compared against 320 real personality profiles selected exclusively from Italian respondents within the IPIP dataset, ensuring cultural consistency and demographic relevance for our target application context.

Figure 4-3 presents the distributional comparison across all Big Five personality dimensions. The analysis reveals significant differences between synthetic and authentic personality score patterns. Real data exhibits more concentrated distributions, reflecting the natural variability and complexity of human personality profiles. Both synthetic generation models demonstrate broader score ranges across most traits, with Mixtral showing particularly wide distributions for Extraversion and Emotional Stability. Notably, the real data displays systematically higher central tendencies for certain traits, particularly Agreeableness and Conscientiousness, suggesting that authentic human responses tend towards more socially desirable characteristics. The synthetic models, conversely, generate more uniform distributions across the personality spectrum, indicating a tendency to explore extreme personality configurations that may be less common in real populations.

To evaluate the psychological authenticity of generated personas (Step 2), we implemented an automated personality assessment protocol using a higher-capacity language model (DeepSeek-R1-Distill-Qwen-32B) as an independent evaluator. This approach tests whether personality traits embedded within biographical narratives remain detectable through automated analysis, providing validation of trait expression effectiveness. The assessment protocol requires the evaluator model to analyse biographical texts and assign numerical scores across all Big Five dimensions using standardised five-point scales. To ensure consistent interpretation, the evaluator receives comprehensive trait definitions derived from established psychological literature, maintaining standardised assessment criteria throughout the evaluation process. Here are some key findings:

**Semi-synthetic advantage:** Real personality combinations perform better with Openness and Agreeableness traits, with Openness showing remarkable accuracy improvements of 25-35 percentage points. We imagine this difference derives from the fact that when we used real personality profiles, the different traits' values are more coherent with real personalities, which enable more natural expression of intellectual curiosity and cooperative characteristics. Agreeableness also benefits consistently, though more modestly, with 7-8 percentage point improvements across both models.

**Synthetic advantage:** Fully synthetic generation performs better for Emotional Stability expression. This finding suggests that when the LLM generates synthetic trait combinations, it tends to create "clean" and simplified versions of emotional stability. For instance, it might generate a person with "high emotional stability" in a very clear-cut manner, without the nuances and contradictions that characterise real individuals. Clearly, in real life, emotional regulation is far more complex. A real person might be emotionally stable at work but anxious in relationships, or generally calm but prone to react poorly to certain specific triggers. In other words, synthetic approaches may create more explicit contrasts in emotional characteristics that facilitate biographical expression.

**Expression challenges:** Conscientiousness and Emotional Stability prove systematically difficult to convey through biographical narratives. These limitations likely stem from the inherent difficulty of expressing systematic behavioural patterns and context-dependent emotional characteristics within personal narrative formats. Such traits may require explicit behavioural examples rather than the implicit characterisation typical of biographical writing styles.



Figure 4-4 - Distribution of similarity and BLEU scores across all pairs of generated biographies.

We also incorporate semantic coherence analysis and lexical variation measurement into the evaluation framework to provide quantifiable measures of generation quality. Our approach employs cosine similarity calculations between text embeddings for semantic relationships, whilst BLEU score analysis measures lexical patterns, enabling examination of how models balance conceptual consistency and expressive diversity. Figure 4-4 shows the

distribution of internal similarities for each dataset, calculated based on semantic similarity (cosine similarity) and lexical similarity (BLEU score) between all pairs of biographies generated by the same model. The analysis examined internal similarity patterns within each dataset by computing semantic coherence and lexical overlap across all biography pairs produced by individual models. Semantic similarity measurements reveal conceptual alignment, whilst BLEU metrics identify surface-level linguistic repetition patterns.

**Lexical Diversity Measurement:** BLEU score analysis across n-gram sequences revealed significant differences between model implementations. The Mixtral-based models (both synthetic and semi-synthetic conditions) exhibited higher and more dispersed BLEU values, indicating greater tendency towards phrase reuse and similar linguistic structures. In contrast, DarkLlama implementations produced lower average BLEU scores with more compact distributions, demonstrating superior lexical diversification.

**Embedding-based Semantic Assessment:** each biographical narrative was transformed into a unified vector representation using Lodestone-base-4096-v1, a BERT-derived model specifically optimised for extended text sequences. Cosine similarity calculations between high-dimensional representations revealed distinct coherence patterns across generation conditions. Our analysis demonstrates that semantic similarity scores between 0.65 and 0.85 across all model configurations, indicating substantial conceptual coherence within generated persona sets. The distribution patterns show relatively high consistency, with most biography pairs achieving similarity scores within this range and only marginal outliers, suggesting effective maintenance of thematic coherence whilst preserving narrative diversity.

**Cross-model Comparative Analysis:** Figure 4-5 shows direct comparison between Mixtral and DarkLlama models when processing identical input. In figure, each point represents a pair of texts referring to the same individual. Average cosine similarity between matched biographies reached 0.6828 for synthetic conditions and 0.6875 for semi-synthetic conditions, confirming conceptual alignment despite independent model training. Corresponding BLEU scores of 0.0381 and 0.0416 respectively—markedly lower than intra-dataset comparisons—demonstrate effective paraphrasing capabilities where models convey similar meanings through distinct lexical formulations.



Figure 4-5 - Relationship between semantic similarity (cosine similarity) and lexical similarity (BLEU score).

**Statistical Correlation Patterns:** we finally calculated Pearson correlation analysis between cosine similarity and BLEU scores. It revealed moderate but statistically significant relationships. Synthetic conditions yielded correlation coefficients of 0.2788 ( $p = 0.000000401$ ), whereas semi-synthetic conditions showed slightly stronger correlations of 0.3127 ( $p = 0.000000011$ ). Spearman rank correlations followed similar patterns (0.2388 and 0.2936 respectively, both  $p < 0.001$ ), indicating consistent but moderate alignment between semantic coherence and lexical similarity measures.

## 4.5 Summary

This chapter has presented a methodology for generating synthetic personas grounded in the Big Five personality model, addressing the need for diverse user representations in social bias detection applications. Our approach has demonstrated that large language models can effectively generate psychologically coherent personas, though with notable variations in trait expression capabilities and significant differences between generation strategies.

The comparative analysis between semi-synthetic and fully synthetic approaches has revealed important insights into personality trait expressibility. Real personality combinations derived from authentic human responses have significantly enhanced generation of some personality traits whereas fully synthetic generation has demonstrated superior performance in other ones.

The evaluation framework has established that generated personas maintain strong semantic coherence across different models whilst demonstrating meaningful lexical diversity. Automated personality assessment has confirmed that different traits exhibit varying degrees of detectability through biographical narratives. The methodology's scalability facilitates the generation of extensive persona datasets that capture edge cases and minority perspectives often overlooked in traditional bias detection approaches, supporting the development of more inclusive and equitable dialogue systems through controlled experimentation with diverse user personalities.

Indeed, within Pilot 2, these generated personas will serve as crucial control variables for creating realistic dialogue scenarios that effectively reveal latent social biases in conversational AI systems. The controlled manipulation of personality traits will enable systematic exploration of how different user characteristics influence system responses, whilst biographical depth will provide contextual richness necessary for natural conversational interactions.

## 5 A Python library for synthetic dialog generation

### 5.1 Motivation

Due to the scarcity and privacy constraints of real conversational data, the advancement of conversational AI research and applications increasingly relies on high-quality, flexible, and reproducible **synthetic dialogues** for training, evaluation, and benchmarking. However, the generation of such dialogues presents several challenges:

- **Standardization:** The absence of standard definitions for dialogue, persona, and event structures complicates the comparison of results across systems and datasets.
- **Abstraction:** There is a need for abstract interfaces that support both single-agent and multi-agent dialogue generation, enabling modular experimentation and extensibility.
- **Fine-grained Control:** Realistic dialogue simulation often requires fine-grained orchestration, such as the injection of instructions, simulation of user behaviors, or enforcement of scenario constraints.
- **LLM Integration:** The use of instruction-tuned Large Language Models (LLMs) for dialogue generation requires seamless integration, prompt management, and memory handling.
- **Scenario and Dataset Management:** The management of complex scenarios, flowcharts, and persona definitions is essential for reproducible research and controlled experimentation.

To address these needs, **SDialog** has been developed as a modular, extensible Python toolkit for synthetic dialogue generation and analysis. As far as we know, SDialog is the first Python toolkit specifically developed to provide a unified, research-oriented framework for synthetic dialogue generation, orchestration, and scenario management with LLMs.

### 5.2 The SDialog Library

SDialog<sup>4</sup> is structured around several core abstractions and modules, each designed to provide flexibility, extensibility, and ease of use in research and development contexts. The following sections describe the main components of the library and their roles in synthetic dialogue generation.

#### 5.2.1 Dialogue Data Structures

The foundation of SDialog consists of data structures that represent the building blocks of a dialogue. These classes provide a standard way to model utterances (turn), events, and entire conversations (dialog), enabling manipulation, serialization, and analysis of dialogues.

##### 5.2.1.1 Turn

A Turn represents a single utterance in a dialogue. It contains the following fields:

- **speaker:** The name or role of the speaker (e.g., “user”, “system”, “Alice”).
- **text:** The utterance text for this turn.

This structure is used to build up the sequence of utterances in a dialogue.

**Example:**

```
from sdialog import Turn

turn = Turn(speaker="Alice", text="Hello, how can I help you?")
print(turn)
```

---

<sup>4</sup> <https://github.com/idiap/sdialog>

### 5.2.1.2 Event

An Event represents an action in the dialogue, which may be an utterance, instruction, or user-defined events. It includes metadata such as:

- agent: The agent responsible for the event (e.g., “user”, “system”).
- action: The type of event (e.g., “utter”, “instruct”).
- actionLabel: A label describing the action (e.g., type of instruction).
- text: The content of the event.
- timestamp: The Unix timestamp of the event.

This structure enables fine-grained tracking of dialogue actions, including orchestration and scenario events.

#### Example:

```
from sdialog import Event
import time

event = Event(agent="System", action="utter", actionLabel=None,
 text="Welcome!", timestamp=int(time.time()))
print(event)
```

### 5.2.1.3 Dialog

A Dialog represents a full dialogue, including turns, events, and scenario metadata. Its fields include:

- formatVersion: Version of the Package used to generate the dialogue.
- model: The model used to generate dialog.
- seed: The random seed used for generation.
- dialogId: Unique identifier for the dialogue.
- complete: Whether the dialogue is complete.
- scenario: Scenario description or metadata (can be a dict or string).
- turns: List of Turn objects representing the conversation.
- events: Optional list of Event objects for detailed event tracking.

The class provides methods for human-readable descriptions, JSON serialization, pretty-printing, and file I/O.

#### Example:

```
from sdialog import Dialog, Turn

dialog = Dialog(
 turns=[
 Turn(speaker="Alice", text="Hi!"),
 Turn(speaker="Bob", text="Hello, Alice!")
]
)
print(dialog) # print as plain text
dialog.print() # pretty print! :)
```

## 5.2.2 Personas and Agents

SDialog supports persona-driven dialogue generation by allowing the definition of detailed character profiles and the simulation of agents that role-play these personas. This abstraction enables the creation of realistic, diverse, and controllable conversational agents.

### 5.2.2.1 Persona

A Persona defines a character profile for role-playing, including attributes such as:

- name: Name of the persona.
- role: Role or occupation (e.g., “barista”, “customer”).
- background: Background information.
- personality: Personality traits.
- circumstances: Current circumstances or context.
- rules: Rules or constraints for the persona.
- language: Preferred language.

Personas are used to generate system prompts and maintain consistent agent behavior.

**Example:**

```
from sdialog import Persona

alice = Persona(
 name="Alice",
 role="barista",
 background="Works at a busy coffee shop.",
 personality="cheerful and helpful",
 circumstances="Morning shift",
 rules="Always greet the customer",
 language="English"
)
print(alice)
```

### 5.2.2.2 PersonaAgent

A PersonaAgent simulates an agent that role-plays a given Persona using an LLM. It maintains a memory of the conversation, supports orchestration for injecting instructions or controlling behavior, and can be seeded for reproducible dialogue generation. The agent can also serialize its configuration and persona for reproducibility.

**Example:**

```
from sdialog import Persona, PersonaAgent

alice = Persona(name="Alice", role="barista", personality="cheerful")
bob = Persona(name="Bob", role="customer", personality="curious")

alice_agent = PersonaAgent("llama2", persona=alice, name="Alice")
bob_agent = PersonaAgent("llama2", persona=bob, name="Bob")

dialog = alice_agent.dialog_with(bob_agent)
dialog.print()
```

## 5.2.3 Orchestration

To enable fine-grained control over dialogue generation, SDialog introduces the concept of orchestrators. Orchestrators are modular components that can inject instructions, enforce constraints, or simulate specific behaviors in agents during a conversation. This section describes the orchestration mechanism and provides examples of built-in orchestrators.

### 5.2.3.1 BaseOrchestrator

The BaseOrchestrator is the abstract base class for all orchestrators. It provides methods for generating instructions, managing persistence, event labeling, and serialization. Orchestrators can be attached to a PersonaAgent to influence its behavior during dialogue generation.

#### Example:

```
from sdialog.orchestrators import BaseOrchestrator

class AlwaysSayHelloOrchestrator(BaseOrchestrator):
 def instruct(self, dialog, utterance):
 if len(dialog) == 0:
 return "Say 'Hello!' as your first utterance."
```

### 5.2.3.2 Example Orchestrators

SDialog provides several built-in orchestrators for common dialogue control patterns:

- SimpleReflexOrchestrator: Triggers instructions based on a condition (e.g., if a certain keyword is present in the utterance).
- LengthOrchestrator: Controls dialogue length by providing instructions to continue or finish the conversation based on the number of turns.
- ChangeMindOrchestrator: Simulates agents changing their mind, optionally with a list of reasons and a probability.
- SimpleResponseOrchestrator: Suggests responses based on similarity to a set of possible responses, using sentence embeddings.
- InstructionListOrchestrator: Provides a sequence of instructions at specific turns, useful for simulating guided user behavior.

#### Usage Example:

```
from sdialog import Persona, PersonaAgent
from sdialog.orchestrators import LengthOrchestrator

assistant = Persona(name="Assistant", role="support agent")
assistant_agent = PersonaAgent("llama2", persona=assistant, name="Assistant")
length_orch = LengthOrchestrator(min=3, max=6)

Add orchestrator using the | operator
assistant_agent = assistant_agent | length_orch
```

## 5.2.4 Dialogue Generation

The DialogGenerator class generates synthetic dialogues using an LLM, given dialogue details and output format. It supports arbitrary system and user prompts, output schemas, and reproducibility via seeding.

**Example:**

```
from sdialog.generators import DialogGenerator

details = "Generate a conversation between a customer and a barista "
 "about ordering coffee."
generator = DialogGenerator("llama2", dialogue_details=details)
dialog = generator()
dialog.print()
```

#### 5.2.4.1 PersonaDialogGenerator

The `PersonaDialogGenerator` class generates dialogues between two personas, enforcing role-play and scenario constraints. It automatically constructs system prompts for both personas and ensures the dialogue starts with a greeting and follows scenario instructions.

**Example:**

```
from sdialog.generators import PersonaDialogGenerator, Persona

persona_a = Persona(name="Alice", role="barista")
persona_b = Persona(name="Bob", role="customer")

generator = PersonaDialogGenerator("llama2", persona_a, persona_b)
dialog = generator()
dialog.print()
```

#### 5.2.5 Datasets and Scenarios

The STAR<sup>5</sup> dataset utilities provide functions for loading, parsing, and describing dialogues, scenarios, flowcharts, and personas from the STAR dataset. These tools support scenario-driven dialogue generation and analysis.

**Example:**

```
from sdialog.datasets import STAR

STAR.set_path("/path/to/star-dataset")
dialog = STAR.get_dialog(123)
dialog.print(scenario=True)

Get scenario description and flowcharts
scenario, description = STAR.get_dialog_scenario_description(123)
print(description)

Get agents for a scenario
system_agent, user_agent = STAR.get_agents_for_scenario(scenario, "llama2")
```

---

<sup>5</sup> <https://github.com/RasaHQ/STAR>

### 5.2.5.1 Scenario Management

Scenario management tools in SDialog allow for the generation of natural language descriptions of scenarios, extraction and visualization of flowcharts, and construction of personas and agents based on scenario metadata.

#### Example:

```
from sdialog.datasets import STAR

scenario = {
 "Domains": ["banking"],
 "UserTask": "Open a new account",
 "WizardTask": "Assist with account opening",
 "Happy": True,
 "MultiTask": False,
 "WizardCapabilities": [{"Task": "open_account", "Domain": "banking"}]
}

system_agent, user_agent = STAR.get_agents_for_scenario(scenario, "llama2")
dialog = system_agent.dialog_with(user_agent)
dialog.print()
```

## 5.3 Practical Examples

This section presents practical examples demonstrating how SDialog can be used for synthetic dialogue generation, orchestration, scenario-driven simulation, and data management. These examples illustrate typical workflows and highlight the flexibility of the toolkit.

### 5.3.1 Example 1: Basic Persona-based Dialogue

The following example demonstrates how to define two personas, instantiate agents for each persona, and generate a simple dialogue between them using an LLM. The agents role-play their respective personas and interact for a fixed number of turns.

```
from sdialog.personas import Persona, PersonaAgent

Define personas
alice_persona = Persona(
 name="Alice",
 role="lovely daughter",
 circumstances="talking with your dad to organize your birthday party."
)
bob_persona = Persona(
 name="Bob",
 role="great dad",
 circumstances="Your daughter will talk to you",
 personality="man of few words",
)

Create agents
alice = PersonaAgent("llama2", alice_persona)
bob = PersonaAgent("llama2", bob_persona)

Generate a dialogue
dialog = alice.talk_with(bob)
dialog.print()
```

#### Example Output:

```
[complete] True
[model] model='qwen2.5:14b' temperature=0.8 seed=13
[seed] 3079960823
— Dialogue Begins —
[Alice] Hi dad! How are you today? I can't wait to talk about my birthday party!
[Bob] Hello, how are you? Sounds like fun, tell me more.
[Alice] I'm great, thanks! For my birthday, I was thinking maybe we could have a small gathering at home.
[Bob] That sounds good. Keep it simple.
[Alice] Perfect! A small party is exactly what I had in mind. Less stress and more fun for everyone. Let's do that.
[Bob] Good idea. Let's do that.
[Alice] Great, dad! Thanks so much. I'll start sending out invites this week. Can't wait to celebrate!
[Bob] Sounds good. Have fun planning.
— Dialogue Ends —
```

### 5.3.2 Example 2: Multi-Agent Dialogue with Orchestration

This example shows how to add orchestration to the dialogue generation process. Orchestrators can control aspects such as dialogue length or simulate behaviors like an agent changing its mind. Here, both a length orchestrator and a mind-changing orchestrator are used to influence the user agent's behavior.

```

from sdialog.personas import Persona, PersonaAgent
from sdialog.orchestrators import LengthOrchestrator, ChangeMindOrchestrator

Define personas
user_persona = Persona(name="User", role="customer")
assistant_persona = Persona(name="Assistant", role="support agent")

Create agents
user = PersonaAgent("llama2", user_persona)
assistant = PersonaAgent("llama2", assistant_persona)

Add orchestrators to control dialogue length and simulate change of mind
length_orch = LengthOrchestrator(min=3, max=9)
change_mind_orch = ChangeMindOrchestrator(probability=0.5,
..... reasons=["changed plants",
..... "new information"])
Add orchestrators to the user agent
user = user | length_orch | change_mind_orch

Generate a dialogue
dialog = assistant.talk_with(user)
dialog.print()

```

#### Example Output:

```

[complete] True
[model] model='qwen2.5:14b' temperature=0.8 seed=13
[seed] 3088682885
— Dialogue Begins —
[Assistant] Hello, how are you?
[User] Hi there, I'm doing well, thanks! How about you?
[Assistant] I'm good, thanks for asking. How can I assist you today?
[User] Just looking to buy a new phone, not sure which model would suit me best. Any recommendations?
[Assistant] Of course! What are your primary needs for the phone—camera quality, battery life, or perhaps
[User] I actually changed my mind. I think I might need a new laptop instead of a phone. Can you help with
[Assistant] Certainly! What will be your main use for the laptop—work, entertainment, or something else?
[User] Thanks, but I think I'll look around some more. Maybe we can chat again later if I need help. Bye!
[Assistant] Sure thing! Feel free to reach out anytime. Have a great day!
— Dialogue Ends —

```

### 5.3.3 Example 3: Scenario-Driven Dialogue Generation with STAR Dataset

SDialog provides utilities for working with the STAR dataset, which contains annotated dialogues and scenarios. The following example demonstrates how to set the dataset path, load a dialogue by its ID, print it with scenario information, and extract scenario descriptions and agents for simulation.

```
from sdialog.datasets import STAR

Set the STAR dataset path
STAR.set_path("/path/to/star-dataset")

Get scenario and description for a given dialog ID (123)
scenario, description = STAR.get_dialog_scenario_description(123)
print(description)

Get agents for a scenario
system_agent, user_agent = STAR.get_agents_for_scenario(scenario, "llama2")

Generate a dialogue
dialog = system_agent.dialog_with(user_agent)
```

### 5.3.4 Example 4: Exporting and Loading Dialogues

SDialog supports exporting generated dialogues to disk in JSON or plain text format, and later loading them for analysis or further processing.

```
Save a dialogue to JSON
dialog.to_file("output/dialogue_001.json")

Save a dialogue to TXT
dialog.to_file("output/dialogue_001.txt")

Load a dialogue from JSON
from sdialog import Dialog

dialog = Dialog.from_file("output/dialogue_001.json")
dialog = Dialog.from_file("output/dialogue_001.txt")
```

### 5.3.5 Example 5: Custom Orchestrators

SDialog allows the definition of custom orchestrators to inject specific behaviors or instructions into the dialogue. The following example shows how to create an orchestrator that ensures the agent starts every conversation with a unique greeting.

```
from sdialog.orchestrators import BaseOrchestrator

class CustomGreetingOrchestrator(BaseOrchestrator):
 def instruct(self, dialog, utterance):
 if len(dialog) == 0:
 return "Start the conversation with a unique greeting!"

Attach the orchestrator to an agent
agent = PersonaAgent("llama2", persona=Persona(name="Bot"))
agent = agent | CustomGreetingOrchestrator()
```

## 5.4 Summary

SDialog provides a comprehensive and extensible framework for synthetic dialogue generation and analysis. The toolkit supports:

- Persona-based role-playing with LLMs, enabling the simulation of realistic and diverse conversations.
- Multi-agent and orchestrated dialogues for the creation of complex, scenario-driven conversational simulations.
- Scenario and dataset integration to facilitate reproducible research and benchmarking.
- Flexible serialization and visualization for downstream tasks and analytical workflows.
- Custom orchestration and extensibility to support advanced research and experimentation in conversational AI.

SDialog is suitable for constructing conversational datasets, evaluating dialogue models, and supporting experimentation in both academic and industrial research contexts related to conversational AI.

## 6 Dialog manager architecture and integration

### 6.1 Current state-of-the-art for LLM-based dialog manager architecture

#### 6.1.1 LLM-based Dialog Manager Systems

The landscape of dialog manager systems has been profoundly transformed by the advent of LLMs which have enabled the development of highly flexible, context-aware, and generalizable conversational agents (Du, 2024), (Hu, 2024). Early dialog systems were predominantly rule-based or statistical, limited in scalability and domain adaptability (Wang H. W., 2023). The introduction of neural language models (NLMs) such as LSTMs and GRUs improved sequence modeling but lacked deep knowledge integration and robust multi-turn reasoning. The rise of pre-trained language models (PLMs) and, more recently, LLMs has enabled end-to-end architectures that unify task-oriented dialog (TOD) and open-domain dialog (ODD), supporting rich multi-turn interactions and cross-domain generalization (Zhang C. D., 2025), (Deng Y. L., 2023), (Deng Y. Z., 2023) (Reimann, 2024).

Major works of LLM-based dialog managers can be described from different perspectives. Recent LLMs with higher capabilities are the core of end-to-end systems that utilize **LLMs directly for natural language understanding, dialog management, and response generation**, simplifying pipelines but raising challenges in controllability, grounding, and interpretability (Deng Y. Z., 2023), (Nehring, 2024). **Proactive dialog managers actively guide conversations toward user goals**. ProTOD (Dong W., 2025) exemplifies this by integrating LLMs with goal-driven reward signals and multi-task planning to improve task success and user satisfaction. Such systems incorporate motivational and strategic interaction capabilities, including clarifying questions and refusal of unreasonable requests (Deng Y. L., 2023), (Dong W., 2025). **Plug-and-play policy planners** employ reinforcement learning (RL) and AI feedback to dynamically guide dialogue policies, improving adaptability across domains (Deng Y. Z., 2023), (Nehring, 2024). **Knowledge-Enhanced Dialogue Managers** employ Dual-feedback knowledge retrieval architectures that separate knowledge retrieval from generation, using iterative feedback loops to refine retrieval accuracy and scalability, particularly for task-oriented systems relying on large or dynamic knowledge bases (Shi T. , et al., 2023). **Full-Duplex Spoken Dialog Systems** consist of Lightweight LLM-based semantic voice activity detection modules that enable real-time turn-taking and scalable full-duplex spoken dialog management, balancing computational efficiency and interaction accuracy (Zhang H. e., 2025).

#### 6.1.2 Multilingual Dialog Manager Systems

Multilingual dialog management is gaining prominence as conversational AI expands globally. LLMs pretrained on multilingual corpora demonstrate strong zero-shot and few-shot capabilities across languages, enabling dialog systems to operate beyond English. Frameworks like DIALIGHT (Hu, 2024) focus on lightweight multilingual development and evaluation of TOD systems, addressing challenges in language diversity and domain adaptation. Multilingual dialog management is further advanced through the recent multilingual LLM architectures. SUTRA (Bendale, et al., 2024) proposes a novel scalable multilingual LLM architecture that decouples concept learning from language learning, enabling efficient cross-lingual transfer and improved performance across languages. Babel introduces an open multilingual LLM (Zhao, et al., 2025) supporting over 25 major languages and covering more than 90% of the global population, demonstrating the feasibility of large-scale multilingual dialog systems.

EuroLLM (Martins, et al., 2024) is a cutting-edge suite of open-weight multilingual LLMs specifically designed to support all official European Union languages along with several additional global languages such as Arabic, Chinese, Hindi, Japanese, and Korean. EuroLLM advances multilingual dialog systems by providing a unified model capable of handling diverse languages with high fidelity. Significantly, the recent Salamandra LLM (Gonzalez-Agirre, et al., 2024) is pretrained from scratch on a carefully curated multilingual corpus comprising text in 35 European languages and code, exclusively sourced from open-access data. This extensive multilingual training enables Salamandra to achieve strong and competitive performance across a wide range of multilingual benchmarks, demonstrating robust capabilities in understanding and generating text in many European languages. Considering the related works in multilingual LLMs and dialog systems, also other interesting studies exist but the aforementioned works are referred here as relevant to ELOQUENCE. (Gonzalez-Agirre, et al., 2024).

### 6.1.3 Dialog Summarization

Dialog summarization has emerged as a crucial natural language processing (NLP) task aimed at condensing multi-turn conversations into concise, coherent summaries that capture essential information and conversational nuances. Recent advances leverage LLMs and sophisticated architectures to improve factual consistency, context-awareness, and informativeness in generated summaries. Dialog summarization is also useful in pruning out irrelevant parts of the dialog and consists of a way to interpret the output of ELOQUENCE dialog manager upon the end of the interaction between the user and the system.

Dialogue summarization enhances response generation by condensing multi-turn interactions into concise representations, improving coherence and context-awareness, especially in multi-domain TOD systems (Wang, et al., 2024).

One prominent approach is the DS-SS framework (Zhang, You, & Wang, 2024), which enhances dialog summarization by fusing factual statements extracted from the source dialog with the dialog itself and segmenting the conversation into topic-coherent chunks. This method enables better encoding of dialog structure, resulting in summaries with higher factual consistency and informativeness, as demonstrated on relevant datasets through both automatic and human evaluations.

Factual consistency remains a key challenge in TOD dialog manager systems; a dialog manager should be able to include all necessary and critical information present in the dialog. Zhu et al. (Zhu, Lau, & Qi, 2025) propose leveraging symbolic knowledge distillation from LLMs to improve smaller pretrained summarization models. By generating both factually consistent and inconsistent summaries and applying contrastive learning, they enhance the factual reliability of summaries without incurring the resource costs of deploying large LLMs directly.

### 6.1.4 Out-Of-Domain Detection

Out-of-domain (OOD) detection is a critical task in dialog manager systems, enabling the system to recognize user inputs that fall outside the supported domain and handle them appropriately to maintain robustness and user trust. This capability is particularly valuable for ELOQUENCE pilot use cases, where preventing user responses from confusing the system is essential, especially in safety-critical applications. Early approaches to OOD detection in dialogue systems often relied on manually labeled OOD samples, which limited scalability and practical applicability. To address this, Zheng et al. (2020) proposed a novel method to generate high-quality pseudo-OOD samples using an autoencoder combined with a generative adversarial network (GAN). This approach trains the model to produce OOD samples that closely resemble in-domain utterances, improving detection performance without requiring extensive labeled OOD data. An auxiliary classifier, further regularizes the generated samples to maintain indistinguishable intent labels, enhancing the system's ability to distinguish OOD inputs effectively (Zheng, Chen, & Huang, 2020).

Context-awareness has also been recognized as essential for effective OOD detection in dialog systems, particularly for multi-turn interactions. A recent framework named Caro incorporates multi-turn dialog context to improve OOD intent detection accuracy by modeling the dependencies across dialogue turns. This approach reflects the reality that user inputs often depend on previous conversational context, making single-turn detection insufficient for robust performance (Lang, Zheng, Hui, Huang, & Li, 2024).

Recent work focuses on likelihood ratio-based methods and generative classifiers for unsupervised OOD detection in task-oriented dialog (Gangal, Arora, Einolghozati, & Gupta, 2020). Their ROSTD dataset, containing real OOD sentences authored by annotators, has been introduced to better benchmark OOD detection in realistic settings. Likelihood ratio approaches reformulate detection by comparing likelihoods under in-domain and out-of-domain models, outperforming traditional likelihood-based methods. Furthermore, learning generative classifiers that compute marginal likelihood ratios at test time has shown superior performance, leveraging training-time labels while maintaining principled probabilistic detection.

In (Wang, et al., 2024), the authors provided a comprehensive evaluation of large language models (LLMs) in zero-shot and few-shot settings for OOD intent detection in task-oriented dialog systems. The authors investigate how well LLMs can generalize to unseen intents and domains without fine-tuning, highlighting the challenges of transferring knowledge from in-domain to out-of-domain queries. While LLMs show promising zero-shot

capabilities, there remains a substantial performance gap compared to fully supervised methods. The study emphasizes the importance of prompt design, instruction tuning, and leveraging domain knowledge to enhance OOD detection. Their experiments suggest that carefully crafted prompts and few-shot examples can significantly improve the detection of OOD intents, making LLMs a viable foundation for scalable dialog systems that must handle novel user queries effectively.

### 6.1.5 Requests For Missing or Ambiguous Information

In recent years, several notable studies have enhanced user-system interaction within dialog manager systems by tackling challenges posed by incomplete or ambiguous user queries. In these scenarios, the dialogue manager is designed to proactively request additional information or seek clarification to better understand the user's intent.

A structured prompt engineering framework is introduced in (Robino, 2025) that leverages LLMs to handle various dialog management tasks in TOD systems. The framework supports dynamic generation of system actions, including requesting additional information when user inputs are incomplete or ambiguous. By structuring prompts to incorporate dialog history, belief states, and database content, the system can generate clarifying questions naturally within the conversation flow.

The work in (Nehring, 2024) replaces traditional dialog managers with a prompt generation module feeding an LLM, integrating inputs from dialog state tracking (DST), natural language understanding (NLU), and database queries. The prompt templates include current user utterances, dialogue history, and partial belief states, enabling the LLM to generate system responses that include requests for missing or ambiguous information. The approach shows how LLMs, guided by carefully engineered prompts, can request additional information dynamically during multi-turn conversations.

Jun Gao et al. (Gao, et al., 2023) propose an adaptive prompt generation framework that automatically constructs prompts for LLMs in TOD systems. The framework generates prompts that reflect the current dialog context, belief state, and candidate slot values, enabling the LLM to act as a dialog agent that can ask clarifying questions or request additional information when necessary. This adaptive prompting reduces manual prompt engineering and improves the system's ability to handle incomplete user queries.

Sarkar et al. (Sarkar, et al., 2025) investigated how rewriting user prompts with LLMs can better express underlying information needs, which is closely related to the dialog manager's role in eliciting missing information. The study shows that LLMs can infer when user queries are underspecified and generate clarifying content or reformulated prompts that implicitly request additional details, improving downstream response quality. This highlights the potential of LLMs to proactively request information within conversational flows.

The study of Atheer et al. (Atheer & Moataz, 2025) evaluates LLMs' ability to simulate user interactions in TOD systems, including scenarios where the system requests additional information from the user. By conditioning LLMs with prompts that include dialog context and task instructions, the models generate realistic system utterances that ask clarifying questions or request missing slot values, demonstrating the feasibility of LLMs performing such dialog management functions.

## 6.2 Proposed dialog manager architecture

A dialog manager (DM) is a central, stateful component of a dialog system responsible for managing the state and flow of the conversation. The DM maintains dialog state variables such as dialog history and unresolved questions, enabling context-dependent processing of user input and coherent conversation management.

A DM keeps track of the dialog state, including user intents, system actions, and context accumulated over multiple turns. Based on the current state and dialogue strategy, the DM decides the next system action. Also, the DM interfaces with task-specific retrieving modules such as databases or expert systems, converting user intent and user slot and entity representations into queries (e.g., SQL) and interpreting their results to informed responses. Having retrieved the relevant information from task-specific retrieving modules, the DM generates semantic instructions (prompts) for the Natural Language Generation (NLG) component to produce responses. Part of DM's responsibilities are to handle problematic user queries (that may be ambiguous, incomplete or out-of-domain) and leverage the history of the dialogue to ensure context is considered.

The ELOQUENCE DM orchestrates the conversation by interpreting user input, maintaining state, deciding system actions, managing external knowledge access, and generating prompts for the system responses, thereby enabling natural, coherent, and goal-directed interactions. The primary duties of the DM into ELOQUENCE project are described next.

Specifically for ELOQUENCE, the DM system under development (T2.3) is designed to continuously track users' goals and autonomously recommend or perform necessary actions to drive the conversation effectively. This system forms a critical part of a modular dialog framework orchestrated by the ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground (T5.3) front-end, which integrates several key components: the DM itself, an Information Retriever, a Dialogue State Tracking (DST) LLM, and a Response Generator LLM, as will be also further discussed in the next section (6.3).

The DM maintains and updates the dialog state by continuously monitoring the user's goals throughout the interaction. It performs several essential duties, including:

- **Querying the Information Retrieval System:** Upon identifying user intents and slot values, the DM sends queries to the information retriever module to fetch relevant data or knowledge, which is essential for grounding responses and fulfilling user requests. A vector store A vector store keep the vector embeddings which are used for similarity search with the current user query.
- **Pruning Irrelevant Conversation History:** To ensure that interactions remain within the processing capabilities of LLMs, the dialog manager carefully regulates the amount of input by monitoring the context window—the maximum number of tokens the model can handle at once. By controlling the length of chat history and applying targeted truncation strategies, when necessary, the system maintains both cost-effectiveness and optimal model performance during chat completion tasks. A common strategy that truncates the chat history effectively sends only the last  $N$  messages (while retaining the system message), while summarizing older messages to preserve essential context while reducing token usage.
- **Identifying Out-of-Domain User Responses:** The system incorporates prompting mechanisms and leverages dialog state information to detect when user inputs fall outside the supported domain or knowledge scope. This capability allows the dialog manager to handle unexpected queries gracefully, either by requesting clarification or redirecting the conversation appropriately.
- **Requesting Additional Information:** When user inputs are ambiguous or incomplete, the dialog manager proactively requests further details to resolve uncertainties, ensuring accurate understanding and response generation.
- **Suggesting Prompts for the Automatic Response Generator:** Based on the current dialog context and retrieved information, the dialog manager formulates semantic instructions or prompts that guide the generator LLM in producing coherent and contextually relevant responses.

The Interactive Playground front-end serves as the orchestrator of the entire dialog system, coordinating interactions among its modules:

1. **User Input Processing:** User utterances are first processed by the natural language understanding components and passed as semantic representations to the dialog manager.
2. **Dialog State Tracking (DST LLM):** The DST module, implemented as an LLM, maintains a structured representation of the dialog state, capturing user intents, slot values, and conversation context over multiple turns.
3. **Information Retrieval:** Triggered by the dialog manager, the information retriever accesses external databases or knowledge bases to supply factual or domain-specific information necessary for task completion.
4. **Dialog Manager Decision Making:** The dialog manager integrates inputs from the DST and information retriever, applies dialog policies and strategies, manages context pruning, detects out-of-domain inputs, and decides on the next system action.

5. **Response Generation:** The generator LLM receives static and dynamic prompts (instructions and dialog context) from the dialog manager and produces natural language responses that are coherent, context-aware, and aligned with the system’s goals.
6. **Output Rendering:** The generated response is delivered back to the user through the front-end interface.

### 6.2.1 Experiments on Dialog Summarization

Currently, a series of experiments on dialog summarization are conducted with the primary goal of condensing multi-turn conversations and pruning irrelevant information. Our experiments utilize the MultiWOZ2.4 (Ye, Manotumruksa, & Yilmaz, 2022) dataset—a widely used benchmark for task-oriented dialog systems—which contains rich multi-domain dialogues, their associated slot-value annotations, and, implicitly, dialogue summaries in the form of user guidelines.

#### 6.2.1.1 Data Preparation & Few-Shot Prompting

We begin by extracting training dialogues from the train\_dials.json file of MultiWOZ2.4. For our in-context learning setup, we select sets of 5 and 10 representative dialog-summary pairs as few-shot examples. These examples are incorporated into the prompt to provide the large language model (LLM) with concrete demonstrations of the summarization task. Each prompt includes a static part with instructions for the task to carry out and a dynamic part with the full conversation history and the final dialog state slot values, ensuring that the model has access to both the narrative flow and the structured semantic information of the dialog.

The summarization model employed in our experiments is the Gemma3-12B LLM (Team, et al., 2025), which is tasked with generating a concise summary of the given dialog based on the provided context and few-shot exemplars.

#### 6.2.1.2 Test Cases Description

We design three distinct test cases to evaluate the impact of different types of input information on the quality of dialogue summarization. For all test cases, Gemma3 was used to perform summarization. The three approaches of the experiments are described next:

1. **Few-Shot Prompting with Dialog Summaries Only:**  
In the first test case, the prompt contains only few-shot examples of dialogues paired with their corresponding summaries. The model receives the conversation history of the test dialog but no explicit dialog state information (slot-values). This baseline case assesses the model’s ability to summarize dialogues relying solely on textual context and exemplar summaries.
2. **Few-Shot Prompting with Dialog, Ground-truth Slot-Values, and Summaries:**  
The second test case augments the prompt by including, alongside the few-shot dialog-summary examples, the last dialog state slot-values of the test dialog. This addition provides the model with structured semantic information representing the current state of the dialog. The purpose is to evaluate how incorporating explicit slot-value information improves the model’s summarization performance by helping it capture all critical details expressed during the conversation.
3. **Few-Shot Prompting with Speech-Input Dialog, ASR Slot-Values, and Summaries:**  
The third test case simulates a more realistic dialog system pipeline. Here, user utterances from the test set are first converted into speech audio using WhisperSpeech (Whisper (Radford A. , et al., 2023) reverse model), a text-to-speech model based on the reversed Whisper architecture. The generated audio is then transcribed back to text using the BUT speech-to-text model developer under T2.1 and described in D2.1, which also outputs the dialog state (slot-values) and domain information. The dialog context for each turn includes the transcribed user utterance and the ground truth system response. After the final turn, Gemma3 is prompted to generate the summary based on the full transcribed dialog and the final dialog state. This case evaluates the robustness of the summarization model when operating on noisy, automatically transcribed input, reflecting real-world conversational AI scenarios.

### 6.2.1.3 Evaluation Metrics

To assess the quality of the generated summaries, we employ several established evaluation metrics:

- **BLEU Score** (Papineni, Roukos, Ward, & Zhu, 2002): Measures n-gram precision between the generated and reference summaries, commonly used to evaluate lexical overlap.
- **METEOR Score** (Banerjee & Lavie, 2005): Considers both precision and recall, incorporating stemming and synonym matching to capture semantic similarity beyond exact word matches.
- **ROUGE Score** (Lin, 2004): Evaluates n-gram and longest common subsequence overlaps, emphasizing recall and fluency in summarization tasks. We chose to use ROUGE-1 score but also other ROUGE variants could be applied.
- **BERT Score** (Tianyi, Varsha, Felix, Kilian, & Yoav, 2019): Uses contextual embeddings from BERT to assess semantic similarity between generated and reference summaries, providing a nuanced evaluation of meaning preservation.

Through these three test cases, we systematically investigate how few-shot prompting, the inclusion of dialog state information, and realistic speech-to-text transcription pipelines affect the performance of LLM-based dialog summarization. This comprehensive evaluation sheds light on the practical benefits of structured semantic input and the challenges posed by noisy real-world data in summarizing complex multi-turn dialogues.

### 6.2.1.4 Dialog Summarization Results

This section reports the results of the dialog summarization experiments across the three distinct test cases. Evaluation metrics across the three test cases are as follows:

|             | BLEU   | ROUGE-1 | METEOR | BERT-F1 |
|-------------|--------|---------|--------|---------|
| Test Case 1 | 0.5429 | 0.7782  | 0.7341 | 0.9448  |
| Test Case 2 | 0.5331 | 0.7760  | 0.6940 | 0.9406  |
| Test Case 3 | 0.4687 | 0.7425  | 0.6570 | 0.9367  |

*Table 1: Dialog Summarization Evaluation Results*

The results indicate that having access to ground truth dialogue state values in the second test case yields better performance compared to the third, where errors introduced by speech transcription and slot recognition affect summary quality. The similarity in performance between the first and second test cases does not suggest that including slot-values does not significantly enhance results when ground truth dialogue turns are provided to Gemma3. Providing the whole ground truth dialog history along with few-shot exemplars seems to be sufficient input for Gemma3 to generate the summary.

Including the dialogue’s state alongside the full dialogue history is particularly important in safety-critical applications, where the accuracy and completeness of the generated summary are paramount. The dialogue state, typically represented by slot-values, serves as a structured record of all critical information exchanged or updated throughout the conversation. This is especially valuable in scenarios where the user may revise their requests or change their mind during the interaction. By providing the LLM with both the unstructured dialogue and the structured state, we ensure that the summarization process captures not only the conversational flow but also the final, agreed-upon details. This dual-input approach helps prevent omissions or misunderstandings, enabling the LLM to produce concise summaries that reliably reflect all essential user goals, criteria, and decisions—an outcome that is vital for maintaining safety, compliance, and user trust in high-stakes dialogue systems.

### 6.3 Integration into Eloquence pilots

The ELOQUENCE system adopts a modular architecture, integrating the various dialogue system components developed within WP2. At the core of this architecture lies the Interactive Playground (IP) interface, which functions as the central intermediary between the end user and the underlying dialogue system. The IP is responsible for orchestrating the system’s functionalities during each turn of the conversation, ensuring seamless interaction and coordination among the different modules. Figure 6-1 illustrates the ELOQUENCE dialogue system architecture, highlighting the distinct modules and their interconnections.

Within this framework, “LLM Instance 1” and “LLM Instance 2” depicted in Figure 6-1 correspond to the DST and Response Generation modules, respectively. These LLM components interact with the DM through the IP, facilitating the flow of information and control throughout the system. A comprehensive description of the ELOQUENCE system architecture, including detailed module specifications and integration strategies, is provided in deliverable D5.2.



Figure 6-1: The IP architecture is designed in a modular way. Our implementations are wrapped in virtual containers running on the same machine to ensure fast communication. To achieve modularity, the expected means of communication is via API.

The DM plays a pivotal role in coordinating the system’s operations. It communicates with both the Retriever and the IP via dedicated API calls. The DM issues queries to the Retriever based on the current dialogue state to obtain relevant information, and manages requests to the IP, ensuring that appropriate prompts are constructed for both the DST and Response Generator modules. By incorporating dialogue policy functionality, the DM maintains control over the conversation flow, supporting robust and context-aware interactions across the ELOQUENCE system.

## 6.4 Summary

The scope of this section is to present the current state of ELOQUENCE's DM, explain its functionality, the different architectural implementation options-and its architecture and give an overall view of how it is going to be integrated into the ELOQUENCE IP as part of the ELOQUENCE system.

The section includes also experiments on dialog summarization; a task that will be needed both for pruning irrelevant information and for producing the summary of the dialogue upon its end.

This section provides an overview and analysis of the current state-of-the-art in LLM-based DM architectures, with a focus on recent advancements and challenges in the field. It begins by surveying LLM-based DM systems, highlighting the shift from traditional rule-based approaches to architectures leveraging LLMs, which offer greater flexibility, adaptability, and natural language understanding for TOD applications. Special attention is given to multilingual DM systems, noting the growing importance of supporting multiple languages to ensure accessibility and inclusivity in diverse user environments.

The section also reviews cutting-edge methods for dialogue summarization, such as the use of mixture-of-experts and role-oriented routing with LLMs, which enhance the ability to generate informative and contextually accurate summaries of multi-turn conversations. Out-of-domain (OOD) detection is addressed as a critical capability, with recent studies showing that LLMs exhibit strong zero-shot and few-shot performance on OOD intent detection, though challenges remain in reliably distinguishing in-domain from out-of-domain queries. Techniques for handling requests for missing or ambiguous information are discussed, emphasizing the need for clarificatory feedback mechanisms and context-aware strategies to resolve user queries that lack specificity or contain ambiguities.

The methodology for handling user feedback, which will be the topic of upcoming D2.4 will give ELOQUENCE's Dialogue System the capability to collect user's level of satisfaction to leverage this feedback to gain some insights on the quality of the generated response given the retrieved information. Also, human feedback, when used as available training data, can be useful to further improve the whole system.

The proposed DM architecture is introduced, detailing its modular design, the integration of LLM-based components for natural language understanding and generation, and the strategies employed for robust dialogue management, including experiments on dialogue summarization to validate performance and scalability.

Finally, the section outlines the planned integration of the DM into Eloquence pilots, demonstrating how the system's advanced capabilities will be deployed and evaluated in real-world multilingual and multi-domain scenarios.

## 7 Conclusions

In this document, we outlined several advancements within the ELOQUENCE project, which is developing innovative technologies for advanced voice and chat assistants. We continued in the spirit of previous deliverables and put an emphasis on handling conversational/speech inputs. We extended the methodology and architecture for speech-enabled FIR from D2.2 with the capability to generate a response to the query. We achieved this through joint architecture where a single speech encoder feeds into two branches: a retrieval branch that finds relevant documents and a question-answering branch that uses an LLM to formulate an answer from the speech and documents. This connector-based system outperforms text-only baselines, though the joint training process can slightly degrade the performance of the retrieval component, an issue targeted for future refinement.

To ensure robust training and evaluation, especially for detecting social biases, we have again resorted to developing methodologies for generating synthetic dialogs and personalities. One method creates realistic user personas based on the Big Five personality model and Italian demographic data, generating psychologically coherent biographies to simulate diverse users. To leverage these models, we also introduced SDialog, a Python library for creating reproducible synthetic dialogues. This toolkit allows for controlled, persona-driven conversations and includes an "orchestrator" to manage conversation flow and simulate specific user behaviors.

Finally, we describe our work on the central component of the dialogue system – the Dialogue Manager, which orchestrates the entire conversational flow. The DM manages the dialogue state, queries the information retrieval system, prunes long conversation histories via summarization to manage the LLM's context limits, and handles ambiguous or out-of-domain user requests. It formulates prompts to guide the response-generating LLM, integrating all modules into a cohesive framework coordinated by the ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground.

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